

ASPECTS OF PREOPERATIVE PREPARATION OF PATIENTS WITH TOXIC GOITER OM FOR SURGICAL TREATMENT

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Summary.

The study included the results of treatment of 112 patients with toxic forms of goiter. Of 112 patients, 24 (21.4%) showed either inefficiency, or intolerance, or complications that arose as a result of long-term antithyroid treatment with thyreostatics. In these patients, a discrete method of plasmapheresis was used in combination with indirect electrochemical plasma oxygenation with sodium hypochlorite with additional ozonation and subsequent reinfusion of detoxified autoplasm. As a result, the period of preparation of patients for surgery was reduced from 12 months in the comparison group to 2 months in the main group.

Key words.

thyrotoxicosis, antithyroid therapy, plasmapheresis.

Relevance. Treatment of toxic forms of goiter is a complex surgical problem [1,5,6]. The most common method of operation remains strumectomy with various options for removing thyroid nodes, which is performed in the vast majority of cases (90.6%) of toxic forms of goiter [1,2,7]. However, a fairly high incidence of postoperative complications and numerous cases of postoperative recurrence of thyrotoxicosis (15-44%), postoperative hypothyroidism (25-63%) indicate a lack of effectiveness and reliability of common surgical tactics [3,4]. ■effective ■

||||| To evaluate the effectiveness of discrete plasmapheresis in preoperative preparation of patients with severe thyrotoxicosis.

Research material . The study is based on the results of treatment of 112 patients with toxic forms of goiter admitted to the surgical department of the multidisciplinary clinic of Samarkand State Medical University in the period from 2012 to 2021.

Results. Of 112 patients, 24 (21.4%) showed either inefficiency, or intolerance, or complications that arose as a result of long-term antithyroid treatment with

thyreostatics. The analysis of the results of drug therapy in patients with toxic forms of goiter at the prehospital stage was carried out. In 8 cases, conservative therapy had no effect, 5 patients developed drug intolerance, 3 had complications (leukopenia, pathology of the gastrointestinal tract).

The collection of anamnesis in patients who received conservative therapy at the prehospital stage showed that it was carried out with thyreostatics: mercazolil, tirizol, prednisolone, dexamethasone. We have analyzed the frequency of complications during conservative therapy, depending on the duration of taking the drug at a dosage that allows achieving a stable remission of the disease.

Basically, these complications occurred in patients with long-term antithyroid therapy, which they were given, despite the lack of effect. 10 patients of the comparison group, despite the negative results of drug therapy, underwent surgical interventions. Due to ineffective preoperative preparation, in 3 (5.8% of the total number of patients in the comparison group) cases, patients with diffuse toxic goiter (DTG) experienced heavy bleeding intraoperatively and in 4 (7.7%) patients in the early postoperative period, thyrotoxic crisis of moderate and severe severity.

These circumstances prompted us to new solutions to improve the results of preoperative preparation of patients with toxic forms of goiter. In contrast to patients in the comparison group, in the main group, patients with severe thyrotoxicosis and patients with contraindicated antithyroid therapy were treated with discrete plasmapheresis (PF) in combination with indirect electrochemical oxygenation (NECHO) of plasma with sodium hypochlorite with additional ozonation and subsequent reinfusion of detoxified autoplasm.

hypochlorite, being a strong oxidizing agent, when added to exfused plasma, carries out the reaction of hydroxylation of organic substances formed during severe thyrotoxicosis. When plasma is processed, sodium hypochlorite releases "active" oxygen, oxidizing triiodothyronine and thyroxine. However, in this case, oxidation products are formed, such as hydroperoxides, during the decomposition of which free radicals are formed, which have a damaging effect on blood cells and on the body as a whole.

Additional ozonation of the exfused plasma after the addition of sodium hypochlorite solution to it makes it possible to increase the detoxifying antithyroid effect, reduce the toxicity of plasma and erythrocytes, and prevent side effects of sodium hypochlorite. The interaction of ozone with organic substrates is accompanied by the activation of oxygen-dependent processes and changes in the physicochemical properties of biological membranes. The interaction of ozone with exfused plasma after adding sodium hypochlorite solution to it is

accompanied by a change in metabolism with an increase in pO_2 , an increase in redox processes, extra- and intracellular processes associated with the production and utilization of energy substrates, the transformation and synthesis of biologically active substances (catecholamines, serotonin, histamine, etc.), increased activity of immunocompetent peripheral blood cells, the inclusion of endogenous detoxification mechanisms (utilization of underoxidized products).

The biological effects of ozone when exposed to the blood are manifested at a level of fairly low concentrations - in the range $[O_3] = 8 - 200 \mu t O_s / IO_2$ and 10 minutes is enough. for saturation of plasma with ozone by bubbling with ozone-oxygen gas mixture. In addition, additional exposure to ozone makes it possible to reduce the exposure time from 4-16 hours (from 8-12 hours on average) to 3-4 hours.

The method of detoxification of the body in severe thyrotoxicosis proposed by us is carried out as follows.

Patients underwent therapeutic plasmapheresis in the amount of 600-800 ml of plasma extraction. Exfused blood plasma under aseptic conditions was collected in sterile hemocones in the calculated volumes.

In compliance with the rules of asepsis, 0.12% (1200 mg/l) sodium hypochlorite solution (g sodium hypochlorite was obtained on an EDO-4 electrochemical unit by oxidation of an isotonic sodium chloride solution) was added with a syringe to a container with exfused plasma in a ratio of 10:1 (i.e., e. 40 ml of NaClO was added to 400 ml of plasma).

The resulting solution was stirred by shaking the container for 2-3 min, and an ozone-oxygen gas mixture was passed through a vial with a plasma solution with sodium hypochlorite by bubbling using the Asia-r clinical Ozonizer for 10 min, then the vial was placed in a household refrigerator (6 -8°C).

Laboratory studies in the experiment showed that the process of oxidation of toxic plasma components, incl. thyroid hormones usually ended by the 3-4th hour of incubation. After 4 hours , the sediment (50-70 ml) was removed from the haemocon using a plasma extractor or aspiration .

From the container with detoxified plasma, 10 ml of plasma was taken for biochemical studies . Convinced of its sufficient detoxification (the effective concentration of albumin increases by more than 1.9 times), the issue of the possibility of reinfusion of this autoplasm as a plasma-substituting medium during the subsequent session of programmed plasmapheresis was decided . The criteria for detoxification of the exfused plasma, making its reinfusion possible, were determined according to N.M. Fedorovsky (2004).

After improvement of the condition of patients and normalization of peripheral blood parameters, surgery was performed.

Clinical example 1. Patient Kh., age 50, No. IB 6395/584 was treated with a diagnosis of diffuse toxic goiter I-V degree, severe thyrotoxicosis, thyrotoxic ophthalmopathy of IV degree, leukopenia, hypochromic anemia, lymphadenopathy, myocardial degeneration H2A, hypertension stage 2A (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Patient X., age 50 years, No. IB 6395/584 was treated with a diagnosis of diffuse toxic goiter I- V degree, severe thyrotoxicosis, thyrotoxic ophthalmopathy of IV degree

She was admitted with complaints of weakness, palpitations, sweating, hand tremors, and weight loss. From the anamnesis: she has been sick since 2008, when she began to notice palpitations, shortness of breath, bulging eyes. On December 24, 2008, she was examined by an endocrinologist for the first time, who confirmed thyroid disease and prescribed Mercazolil at a dose of 30 mg per day, which she received for 1.5 years. However, complete remission of the disease was not achieved. In 2011, a blood test revealed leukopenia (leukocytes - $2.1 \times 10^9 / l$) and hypochromic anemia (erythrocytes - $2.1 \times 10 / l$; Hg 84 g / l), there were signs of intolerance to the drug - urticaria. The drug was canceled and prednisolone was prescribed at a dose of 60 mg per day in courses for two weeks. The effect of the treatment was temporary, in addition, the drug also appeared urticaria. In 2012, hormone therapy was canceled, after which the phenomena of thyrotoxicosis began to progress. Weight loss was noted (for 8 months by 15 kg), hand trembling, palpitations increased, bulging eyes increased. In the same period of the disease, a stomach ulcer was discovered. The question of surgical treatment of the patient was raised only in 2013, in connection with which she was hospitalized. Upon admission, the patient's condition was severe, body weight was below normal, the skin was pale and moist. There are no edema. Cardiovascular system: heart sounds are muffled, the rhythm is wrong, heart rate is 130 per 1 minute. A/D 180/100 mm Hg Pulsation in the peripheral vessels is preserved. The results of the survey: ECG - registered ventricular extrasystoles, the dynamics of the ST segment is

not changed, heart rate -110-116 per minute. Special status: the thyroid gland is enlarged, heterogeneous on palpation, painless, mobile. The cervical lymph nodes are not palpable. Positive symptoms of Graefe, Mobius, Diehl-Ritz. The level of thyroid hormones: T4 - 250 nmol / l (normal 60-160 nmol / l); T3 - 5.6 nmol / l (norm 1.2 - 2.8 nmol / l); TSH - 0.1 mIU / l (0.17 - 4.05 mIU / l). The patient underwent 5 sessions of plasmapheresis, which allowed to reduce the level of thyroid hormones: T4 - 154 nmol / l; T3 - 2.5 nmol / l; TSH - 0.12 mIU / l. Against this background, on April 17, 2000, an operation was performed - subtotal subfascial resection of the thyroid gland. The operation and postoperative period in the patient proceeded without complications. Discharged for 7 days. At the control examination after 2 years, there was no recurrence of the disease.

This observation clearly demonstrates that long-term conservative treatment was ineffective when using both thyreostatics and hormonal agents. In addition, the patient developed intolerance to these drugs, and then complications from the blood and gastrointestinal tract.

According to numerous recommendations, 5 to 7 plasmapheresis sessions are sufficient to prepare patients with toxic forms of goiter for surgery. This number of sessions also served as a guideline in the treatment of our patients.

The effectiveness of plasmapheresis was monitored by studying the dynamics of T4 hormones; Tz; TSH. Figures 2-4 show the concentration of these hormones in 14 patients before and after discrete plasmapheresis.

Fig. 2. T4 level in patients with toxic goiter before and after plasmapheresis.

Fig. 3. T3 level in patients with toxic goiter before and after plasmapheresis.

Fig. 4. TSH level in patients with toxic goiter before and after plasmapheresis.

The analysis showed that the concentration of the hormone T4 and T3 before treatment in all patients with toxic forms of goiter was 3.5-4 times higher than the normal level. At the same time, in these patients, TSH was below normal or at its lower limit. We did not observe a direct dependence of the TSH value on the severity of thyrotoxicosis. During treatment, the concentration of T4 and T3 approached the norm or to its upper limit, and TSH remained at the same level or slightly increased.

Criteria for the effectiveness of preoperative preparation in the group patients with severe forms of thyrotoxicosis treated with plasmapheresis (14 patients), compared with patients who received medication preparation (10 patients), there

were blood pressure and pulse indicators before, during and after performing surgical intervention. Increased blood pressure and increased heart rate in comparison with the individual norm for each patient, we regarded as an attack of hypertension and tachycardia caused by this disease.

At admission, all patients with the ineffectiveness of conservative therapy had symptoms hypertension and tachycardia, in the comparison group, hypertension occurred in 3, severe tachycardia in 4 patients.

After PF in combination with NECHO of plasma with sodium hypochlorite with additional ozonation and subsequent reinfusion of detoxified plasma in the main group, 14 patients with tachycardia (up to 90 beats per minute) and hypertension persisted only in 2 patients.

Table 1.

Efficiency of preoperative preparation (before surgery)

Comparison groups	Study effect (outcome), tachycardia and hypertension		
	no effect	effective	Total
Main group (plasmapheresis)	2	12	14
Comparison group (thyrostatics)	6	4	10
Total	8	16	24

The effect of preparing for PF and medication preparation in absolute terms during the operation is presented in Table 1 . According to these data, we calculated key indicators effectiveness of preoperative preparation in the group of patients who was assigned to PF, compared with the comparison group, which medical preparation was carried out. The data presented in the table indicate a rather low the frequency of adverse outcomes in thyroid resection in patients prepared with PF compared with patients prepared with medication.

In the postoperative period, the ratio of patients and scores intervention effectiveness results remained unchanged.

Clinical example 2. Patient L., aged 50, case no. 6397/585, was on treatment from 06/08/2017 to 06/28/2017 with a diagnosis of diffuse toxic goiter III degree, severe thyrotoxicosis, exophthalmos II degree, thyrotoxic heart, paroxysmal tachycardia, IHD, angina pectoris 1 f.cl., atherosclerotic cardiosclerosis, gastric ulcer (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Patient L., aged 50, was on treatment with a diagnosis of diffuse toxic goiter III degree, severe thyrotoxicosis, exophthalmos II degree, thyrotoxic heart, paroxysmal tachycardia.

On admission, the patient complained of an increase in the size of the neck, 15 kg weight loss in one year, foreign body sensation in the eyes, frequent stools (up to 4-5 times a day) (Fig. 3.12). History of the disease: sick since 1995, when pains in the heart appeared, heartbeat. Seen by an endocrinologist. Received courses of treatment: Mercazolil at a dose of 40 mg/day, prednisolone up to 30 mg/day, iodine preparations, nitrates, verapamil, aspirin, piracetam, sedatives. Within 3 years on the background of treatment, there was a temporary improvement with subsequent relapse thyrotoxicosis. At the same time, the doses of Mercazolil and Prednisolone gradually increased. Since 1998, after eating, pain in upper abdomen. FGDS revealed a stomach ulcer. Locally: the thyroid gland is visible on examination, elastic, dense, painless on palpation. Mobius, Murphy, Graefe symptoms are positive. Ultrasound: isthmus 9.1 mm, right lobe 2.2 cm, left lobe 28.7 cm, the echostructure is heterogeneous, additional formations are not visualized. Indications for surgery were given. 4 sessions scheduled for preparation PF in combination with NECHO of plasma with sodium hypochlorite with additional ozonation and subsequent reinfusion of detoxified plasma. Indicators of thyroid hormones before plasmapheresis sessions: T4 - 290 nmol / l (norm 60-160 nmol/l); T3 - 5.1 nmol / l (norm 1.2-2.8 nmol / l); TSH - 0.17 mIU / l (norm 0.17 - 4.05 mIU / l). After 6 sessions of plasmapheresis: T4 - 170 nmol/l; T3 - 2.4 nmol / l; TSH - 0.19 mIU / l. On June 20, 2017, the operation "Subtotal subfascial resection thyroid gland". Dynamics of heart rate and blood pressure on admission, during time and after surgery are presented in Table 3.3. The postoperative period was uneventful, the patient was discharged in a satisfactory condition on June 28, 2017.

The given example of the treatment of patient V. confirms that, despite the severity of thyrotoxicosis and its complications (thyrotoxic heart), preoperative therapy, including plasmapheresis sessions, made it possible to prepare the patient for surgery and perform it without any negative consequences.

After preoperative preparation, these patients underwent surgery without PF. Patients who had severe thyrotoxicosis and the ineffectiveness of drug euthyroidism for more than 3 months or intolerance to thyreostatics were prescribed β -blockers and 1% Lugol solution for 2 weeks and before surgery, the 6th session of PF in combination with plasma NECHO with sodium hypochlorite with additional ozonation and subsequent reinfusion detoxified plasma.

The developed method of plasmapheresis in patients with toxic forms of goiter made it possible to choose the optimal method of preoperative preparation. As a result, the period of preparation of patients for surgery was reduced from 12 months in the comparison group to 2 months in the main group (Fig. 6). In addition, the side effects of thyreostatics, such as leukopenia, agranulocytosis, and side effects from the digestive tract, were eliminated.

Conclusions. The use of plasmapheresis in combination with indirect electrochemical oxygenation of plasma with sodium hypochlorite with additional ozonation and subsequent reinfusion of detoxified plasma in the group of patients with severe forms of thyrotoxicosis and intolerance to drugs leads to a significant decrease in hormonal levels, normalization of the function of the cardiovascular system and in the early postoperative period allows leveling cases of thyrotoxic crisis.

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